

Languages & Thinking

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Abstract: Speaking more than one language can change the way of thinking. In this research I will discuss how can learning more than one language effect and change the way of thinking positively. Many language-learning scientists and psychologists proved this approach, based on experience on people since their early years until they grew up. Moreover, by exposing into different cultures and societies they became more advanced, smart, and improved their awareness. They became more creative in solving issues and looking to things in different point of views. The goal of this research is to confirm the role of learning languages in improving the way of thinking. In addition, to encourage people to learn new languages to expand their horizons.

Keywords: Language, Learning, Thinking, Cultures, English.

I. HOW CAN LEARNING NEW LANGUAGES ENRICH KNOWLEDGE AND CHANGES THE WAY OF THINKING?

A study by Dr. Thomas Bak - a lecturer at Edinburgh's School of Philosophy, Psychology and Language Sciences - shows that bilingual people performed better in tests than people who speak only one language and showed high rates in general intelligence and reading. It also increases the brain abilities to focus and avoid distractions (figure 1). A scientific study in Sweden showed that people who study language subjects their brain size expanded and people who ignored language subjects their brain remained the same.

Speaking more than one language can make people more conscious, more creative thinkers and attentive listeners who can be successful communicators. Language is the key to the door of culture. Once you open that door, you expose your mind to a new horizon of knowledge and life experiences. The more doors you open the more you enrich your mind and your way of thinking (figure 2).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Learning new language makes people more understanding for other people around the world. It makes People understand and accept other society's traditions, ways of thinking and living around the world. Which leads to living peacefully and successfully (figure 3).

Figure 2

A study by the American Academy of Neurology showed that Multilingualism is very important on the mental health level (figure 4). It delays the signs of Alzheimer symptoms. People who speak Multilanguage experiences Alzheimer disease later than the monolingual people do.

Figure 2

A study by (Jennifer Krizman, Viorica Marian, Anthony Shook) Showed that the ability to switch between two languages or more makes the brain more focused in the important things and gives the ability to control and distinguish the important information. Speaking more than one language gives more opportunities to get a good career. Now A days, companies prefer to hire people who have more than one language in their CV. They have higher opportunities to get a job more than others do (figure 5).

Figure 2

Learning new language stimulates creativity. Exposing your mind to a new culture makes your mind more flexible, and opens new horizons of thoughts. It also, increases the mind ability to comprehend and observe new information (figure 6). Learning new language improves your first language. It makes your brain distinguish the differences between their grammar and vocabularies. It also improves your memory. Learning more than one language increases self-esteem. It makes you more confident to speak and not afraid of making mistakes.

Figure 2

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